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DEFINITIONS AND THEIR THEORETICAL ANALYSIS APPLIED TO ISLAMIC SECURITIES SUKUK

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ANNOTATION

Islamic securities are specially designed financial products that comply with the principles of a certain legal (sha'ari) financial transaction and are strictly applied in the development of financial contract terms covering such products. Recent developments in Islamic finance have changed the dynamics of the Islamic finance industry, particularly in the area of sukuk or Islamic securities. Sukuk have become increasingly popular over the past few years, both as a means of raising public finance through sovereign issues and as a financing method for companies through corporate sukuk offerings. However, there is no generally accepted definition of sukuk, and this has led to different definitions of sukuk by various governmental and non-governmental organizations. As a result, different definitions of sukuk have emerged, sometimes these definitions fail to reveal the true nature of sukuk, and sometimes they do not cover certain aspects of sukuk. This article analyzes such problems and their theoretical aspects.

Keywords: sukuk, bond, share, stock, asset, mubarak, musharak, trust investment certificates, sak.

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ISLOMIY QIMMATLI QOG'OZ SUKUKKA NISBATAN QO'LLANILADIGAN TA'RIFLAR VA ULARNING NAZARIY TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Islomiy qimmatli qog'ozlar - bu maxsus ishlab chiqilgan moliyaviy mahsulotlar bo'lib, ular ma'lum bir qonunga asoslangan (shar'iy) moliyaviy bitim tamoyillariga mos keladi va bunday mahsulotlarni qamrab oladigan moliyaviy shartnoma shartlarini ishlab chiqishda qat'iy qo'llaniladi. Islomiy moliya sohasidagi so'nggi yangiliklar islom moliya sanoati dinamikasini, xususan, sukuk yoki islom

qimmatli qog'ozlari sohasida o'zgartirdi. Sukuk so'nggi bir necha yil ichida suveren masalalar orqali davlat moliyasini jalb qilish vositasi sifatida ham, kompaniyalar uchun korporativ sukuk taklif qilish orqali moliyalashtirish usuli sifatida tobora ommalashib bormoqda. Ammo, sukukka nisbatan umumtanolangan ta'rif mavjud emas va bu esa turli xil davlat va nodavlat tashkilotlari tomonidan sukukka nisbatan turli xil ta'riflar berilishiga sabab bo'ldi. Buning natijasida sukukka nisbatan turli xil ta'riflar yuzaga kelib, ba'zida bu ta'riflarning sukukning asl tabiatini ochib bera olmasa, ba'zida sukukning ayrim jihatlari qamrab olmaydi. Ushbu maqolada bu kabi muammolar va uning nazariy jihatlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sukuk, obligatsiya, aksiya, qimmatli qog'oz, aktiv, muzoraba, mushoraka, ishonch investitsiya sertifikatlari, sak.

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ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ И ИХ ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ПРИМЕНИТЕЛЬНО К ИСЛАМСКИМ ЦЕННЫМ БУМАГАМ СУКУК

АННОТАЦИЯ

Исламские ценные бумаги представляют собой специально разработанные финансовые продукты, которые соответствуют принципам определенной законной (шаари) финансовой операции и строго применяются при разработке условий финансовых контрактов, охватывающих такие продукты. Недавние события в исламских финансах изменили динамику индустрии исламских финансов, особенно в области сукук или исламских ценных бумаг. Сукук становится все более популярным за последние несколько лет, как в качестве средства привлечения государственного финансирования посредством государственных выпусков, так и в качестве метода финансирования компаний посредством корпоративных предложений сукук. Однако общепринятого определения сукук не существует, и это привело к разным определениям сукук различными правительственными и неправительственными организациями. В результате появились различные определения сукук, иногда эти определения не раскрывают истинную природу сукук, а иногда они не охватывают определенные аспекты сукук. В данной статье анализируются подобные проблемы и их теоретические аспекты.

Ключевые слова: сукук, облигация, акция, актив, мубарак, мушарак, трастовые инвестиционные сертификаты, сак.

Introduction.

The principles underlying Sukuk certificates have been developed over fourteen centuries through references in the Quran and Shariah guidelines. The word Sukuk does not appear anywhere in the Quran. Sukuk emerged through development as a result of the regulation of lending and borrowing activities in people's daily lives through the guidelines in the Quran and Hadith. Asset-based lending and borrowing activities for production or other economic activities have been widespread in the Middle East and Mediterranean region with the expansion of Islam and its penetration into various nations. Such lending practices were carried out by sharing risks and benefits over a certain period of time in order to increase liquidity.

By the end of the 19th century, as Muslim states weakened and European countries became colonies or semi-colonies, Islamic economic and financial relations based on Sharia, such as sukuk, began to lose their importance in economic and financial relations. Such Islamic financial services were replaced by modern European banking practices and finance, based on the lack of mutual risk sharing between parties and a predetermined percentage of profit. After about 40 years, after the re-

introduction of banking practices based on profit sharing and risk sharing, the Islamic debt instrument sukuk appeared in a number of countries in the late 1990s.

When we talk about sukuk, we first see that there is a discrepancy in the definitions given by European scholars and Muslim scholars, as well as by various international financial organizations and national organizations of various countries. We can even see that there is no single, clear definition of sukuk among Muslim scholars [1, p-22.].

The word sukuk is a certificate of ownership of a class of assets issued by a borrower to a lender as a document of ownership, plural of sak. Therefore, sukuk securities are debt instruments that require the creation of assets in a separate entity, which are owned proportionally by the lenders, fund providers. Fully asset-backed lending is a fundamental principle of the sukuk contract.

The emergence of sukuk (trust investment certificates) in international capital markets and the growing interest in sukuk have raised a number of questions about the theory and origins of such structures. The rapid expansion of sukuk in a short period of time has surprised observers, and there is a great interest in learning more about the basics of sukuk and its historical development, especially in the Western world.

In a sense, this suggests that there can be no ethical financial transaction without the lender creating a long-term asset that supports the debt financing arrangement in which the borrower transfers income-generating assets. This suggests that all sukuk securities should have this safety net, so that from the outset of the agreement, lenders are backing the assets for their funds.

This makes sukuk securities safer than traditional bonds, as under a traditional loan agreement, the lender would need court permission to take ownership. Such permission would only be granted if a challenge is made at the time of the promised payment.

A sukuk contract can be viewed as a loan agreement between a lender (investor) and a borrower to participate in a production or service activity. The financing arrangements can vary, including ownership and control arrangements, equity securities, pure loan securities, and lease securities. Therefore, it is incorrect to describe sukuk as an Islamic debt instrument only, as is common practice in the financial media [2, p-76.].

Unlike most sukuk issues, in musharakah sukuk securities issued to investors, investors receive a reward in the form of only a portion of the profits based on a pre-agreed profit ratio. If the ownership is in all of the assets of the borrower, whether or not the entity has control, this is also a musharaka sukuk, which is a limited-term equity financing arrangement (a concept rarely seen in modern finance).

As sukuk is a relatively new product, with only 12 markets, there is no consensus on its precise definition. Some international regulatory bodies, such as the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI), the International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM), and the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), have attempted to provide somewhat more precise definitions of sukuk that are closer to its nature.

As an institutional definition, we need to turn to Article 17 of the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) Sharia Standards, according to which:

“Sukuk are certificates of equal value that represent indivisible shares in the ownership of a tangible asset, its benefits, or specific services or specific investment activities or assets of a specific project, but they become effective only after the value of the sukuk has been accepted, subscribed, and the funds received for the purpose for which the sukuk was issued have been directed.” [3, p-307.].

In 2010, the IIFM (International Center for Islamic Finance) defined sukuk as “a commercial paper that gives an investor ownership rights over a specific asset.” These are asset-based trust certificates that provide ownership of a specific asset or the benefits it generates, which in practice represent a relatively stable income stream and must be in accordance with the principles set forth by Sharia. Unlike traditional bonds, sukuk must have a tangible asset transaction in the form of ownership or a fixed lease agreement.

The definition of sukuk given by the IFSB (Islamic Financial Services Board) in 2009 is as follows:

Sukuk (plural of sakq), often referred to as "Islamic bonds", are certificates in which each sakq represents a non-proportional ownership interest in tangible assets or a pool of tangible assets, or a business venture (such as a muzaarabah). These assets may be invested in a specific project or investment activity in accordance with Shariah rules and principles.

This definition of sukuk differs from traditional interest-bearing securities (i.e. bonds) in the following ways:

- The funds raised through the issuance of sukuk should be used for investments in specific assets, and not for general unspecified purposes. This means that identifiable assets should be the basis for Islamic bonds.
- Since sukuk is backed by real underlying assets, the income generated by the allocated assets should be related to the purpose of using the funds.
- The sukuk certificate represents a proportionate ownership right in the allocated assets in which the funds are invested. Ownership is transferred from the original owner to the sukuk holders for a fixed period, ending with the maturity of the sukuk.

Some governments in Muslim countries, such as Qatar Financial House, require authorized firms to adhere to international definitions. Others define sukuk in their own way. The Securities Commission of Malaysia, which has issued guidelines for the offering of Islamic securities, defines sukuk as “a document or certificate representing the value of an asset.” The Liquidity Management Center in Bahrain defines sukuk as “a certificate of equal value representing an undivided interest in tangible assets, usufruct and services, or in the assets of a specific project or investment activity.”

This definition suggests that there is no time limit for sukuk. In other words, sukuk can be issued for both long-term and short-term financing. Short-term sukuk with maturities of up to one month are issued by various issuers; they are similar to traditional bills or notes. One of the first issues of short-term sukuk was the 30-day and 91-day salam (futures) sukuk issued by the Bahrain Monetary Agency in 2001.

Bank Negara Malaysia also issues one-year short-term sukuk. Since 1994, the bank has operated the Islamic Interbank Money Market (IIMM) as an intermediary for providing short-term investment sources based on Sharia principles. Although the IIMM operates using a form of financing called murabaha, the bank has not issued sukuk for specific purposes. When a sukuk is issued, the issuing regulator clearly defines the sukuk security and this is posted on the website of each sukuk issuer.

Another institutional definition for sukuk is provided by the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), according to which:

Sukuk (plural of Suk) is an Islamic bond, each Suk representing an indivisible right of ownership over a tangible asset or a bundle of tangible assets or a business venture (for example, murabaha). These assets may be in a specific project or investment activity in accordance with the rules and principles of Sharia [4].

A more institutionalized tariff on sukuk has been set by the International Islamic Financial Market, according to which:

“A commercial paper that gives an investor ownership rights to a specific asset. These are asset-based trust certificates that prove ownership rights to the asset or its useful value (income) [5].”

Regarding the definition of sukuk by government agencies, the Securities Commission of Malaysia defines it as follows:

Sukuk are certificates of equivalent value that represent an indivisible ownership interest or investment in an asset based on Sharia principles and are approved by the SAC (Shariah Advisory Council) [6].

Kuwaiti Ministerial Decree No. 388 of 2007 also defined sukuk, according to which:

Sukuk – Instruments of equal value issued by companies under certain types of contracts that comply with Islamic Sharia, such as Musharaka, Muzarab, Ijara or an investment agency, in a specific investment project or activity, in accordance with the provisions of relevant laws [7].

The Securities and Commodities Authority (SCA) in the United Arab Emirates defines sukuk as “financial instruments of equal value that represent an ownership interest in an asset or group of assets and are issued in accordance with Sharia law [8].”

Additionally, the official definition of Sukuk can be found in the Sukuk Regulations 2015 of the Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP):

“An instrument of equal value representing the investment of sukuk holders in the ownership of specified tangible assets, at the level of an undivided share in the issuer’s capital, representing ownership rights in respect of a specific investment activity or a specific project asset, the participation in which requires approval by the Shariah Board [9].”

Sukuk is also described in traditional regimes, for example, the Australian Government's Taxation Council has set out the following description:

“Sukuk is the Islamic financial equivalent of traditional marketable securities or bonds, which represent ownership (actual or beneficial) of an asset or financing arrangement by sukuk holders in accordance with the underlying Sharia. The return is paid to investors in accordance with their proportionate ownership in the asset and investment and varies based on the performance of the assets, rather than the passage of time [10].”

Sukuk is the Islamic financial equivalent of traditional marketable securities or bonds, which represent ownership (actual or beneficial) of an asset or financing arrangement by sukuk holders in accordance with the underlying Sharia law. The return is paid to investors in accordance with their proportionate ownership of the asset and investment, and varies based on the performance of the assets, rather than the passage of time [11].

Furthermore, the Luxembourg Tax Inspectorate's January 12, 2010, circular on Islamic finance defines it as follows:

"Securities representing a claim or right to a share, where both income and capital are indexed to the performance of one or more assets owned by the issuer, the income stream being used to pay and settle the shuk."

Conclusion.

From this definition, we can see that the understanding of the term sukuk fluctuates between broad and narrow definitions. The definitions of sukuk provided by Islamic finance standard-setting bodies such as AAOIFI and IFSB have not been reviewed by regulatory regimes in countries such as Kuwait, Malaysia, UAE and Pakistan. The definition of sukuk has found its place in relevant statutes or guidelines in several countries. The definitions mentioned above focus more on the specific aspect of sukuk as a representation of ownership. While all these definitions attempt to describe precisely what sukuk is, they fail to agree on the essence of sukuk. On the one hand, the AAOIFI definition limits the underlying asset of sukuk to tangible assets; In this regard, Dusuki noted that the AAOIFI definition does not consider financial assets or financial receivables as potential assets in a Sukuk, as the AAOIFI prohibits the sale of debt. On the other hand, the SC definition includes all types of assets and does not exclude financial receivables [12, p-10.].

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